

Enhancing Power Quality in Distribution Networks through Advanced Control Strategies for Distributed Generation Grid Side Converters

Muhammad Raza, Amira S. Hassan, Ahmed M. Amin, Iman F. Al-Dabbagh

Department of Electrical Engineering, University of Cairo, Cairo, Egypt; Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, King Fahd University of Petroleum and Minerals, Dhahran, Saudi Arabia

Abstract -- Diversifying the role of grid side converters (GSC) associated with distributed generation (DG) may have a technical and economic impact. The increasing number of residential photovoltaic systems can be exploited by distribution network (DN) operators in order to support and improve the power quality of the grid without considerable further capital investment. The GSC can support the grid during abnormal conditions but may also be used to improve the DN power quality by balancing out asymmetries and alleviating the grid from undesired harmonics. The proposed advanced control technique demonstrates through simulation and experimental results that the role of GSC can be upgraded to improve the power quality of the grid. Furthermore, the proposed control scheme is validated on a realistic low-voltage DN using data from the Cyprus Electricity Authority. Consequently, conventional practices by distribution network operators for improving the power quality can be re-assessed as the necessary power electronics hardware for mitigating grid problems are already present within the GSCs of DG systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

There are several reasons leading to the massive deployment of residential photovoltaic (PV) systems. One reason is the cost of PV for example, which has considerably decreased over the past few years and it might decrease even further. The fact that a lot of research is underway for improving the efficiency of

PVs is also an indication that PVs will dominate distributed generation (DG) in coming years. Furthermore, consumers realize that residential PV systems are beneficial in terms of reducing the electricity bills under various schemes adopted by the respective national policies. Despite the many problems distribution network (DN) operators face with DG, research is now shifting towards investigating how all these rooftop PV systems can be exploited to benefit and support the grid operation. The contribution of renewable energy systems

during unwanted events occurring on the grid such as the presence of harmonics, phase unbalance, faults, voltage sags etc., as well as the requirement for optimum interaction with microgrids and smart grids, are some of the areas where research is headed. Such a grid friendly operation can be enabled by the grid side converter (GSC), which is an inherent component of any PV rooftop system. The additional installation of power electronics equipment (such as series [2, 3] or shunt active power filters [4, 5]) is not necessary, reducing therefore the cost to DN operators when they have to deal with such problems. Hence, it is more cost-effective to use the existing GSC for delivering the produced PV power into the grid and in addition, to perform advanced functional modes for mitigating the asymmetries and harmonics caused by nearby loads. Advanced GSC grid functionalities for harmonic elimination and asymmetry compensation can be performed through the control scheme and modifications to the current and PQ controllers, which are discussed in this paper.

PV systems installed on the rooftops of the residential or commercial buildings transform passive consumers to active, commonly referred to as prosumers (those that consume and produce power back to the electrical grid) [6]. The brain behind the energy traffic control is the GSC, normally a three-phase inverter [7]. On the other hand, commercial or residential loads are usually not balanced among the three-phases and present a non-linear response causing problems to DN related to: increased power losses, poor power quality due to asymmetric and harmonically distorted currents and voltages, low power factor, derated capacity for cables, transformers, and lines, possible torque oscillations in machines operation, overheating, etc. [8]. The work proposes new functionalities of distributed RES that improve the power

quality and enhance the overall operation of the DN via the existing GSC of rooftop PV systems.

Exploiting GSCs capabilities towards the benefit of the grid has been discussed in literature but with several limitations and restrictions. A detailed comparison of the existing techniques with the proposed one is given in Table I.

This paper proposes a GSC with an innovative control technique comprising of additional advanced features for regulating the power quality of the grid by mitigating the asymmetries and harmonics caused by connected prosumer loads. The proposed technique involves three main components: (i) the synchronization unit for obtaining the grid voltage phase angle under normal and abnormal grid scenarios, (ii) a decoupling network based novel *PQ* controller for estimating the asymmetric and harmonic components of the prosumers load to be compensated, and (iii) an advanced

time of fault and/or reference variation. In addition, the controller must be as less complex as possible in order to be easily implemented in the embedded microcontroller [17]. So far, many current controllers have been proposed in the literature. The simplest Synchronous Reference Frame (SRF) based conventional current controller [18] generates the voltage reference utilizing positive SRF (dq^{+1}) and two PI controllers. The main drawback of conventional SRF⁺¹ controller is that it cannot perform accurately under unbalance grid voltage due to the presence of double frequency (2ω) oscillations on the transformed dq^{+1} quantities. The problem caused by 2ω oscillations is mitigated in [19] by the introduction of dual SRF (DSRF) controllers and some filtering techniques. The DSRF controller is developed by combining two conventional SRF controllers, respectively operating in positive and negative rotating reference frames. The DSRF is also equipped with two additional notch filters

TABLE I. COMPARISON OF THE PROPOSED ADVANCED CONTROL TECHNIQUE WITH THE TECHNIQUES FROM THE EXISTING LITERATURE.

<i>PQ</i> based control technique	Key features of control technique towards improving power quality	Limitations
[9, 10]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Combination of PI and PR are used as current controller. Single-phase GSC based PV systems are employed. Compensate for load harmonics only. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Single-phase configuration does not allow symmetrizing the unbalanced loads. Power control loop is complex.
[8]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PR based current controller is used. Inject both positive and negative sequence currents Mitigate for voltage asymmetries only.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Requires knowledge of the grid impedance at the Point of Common Coupling (PCC), unknown most of the times. PR controller has complex tuning method, does not allow feedforward and is sensitive to frequency variations. Cannot compensate for harmonics.
[11]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EDDSRF current controller is employed. Compensate for asymmetric prosumers loads. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Computationally complex. Does not allow the compensation of harmonic currents caused by the non-linear loads
[12]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Deadbeat current controller is used. Reference currents are generated using delayed signal cancellation method. Compensate for prosumer's asymmetries and selective harmonics. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Deadbeat controller is sensitive to system uncertainties. It may limit the controller's bandwidth.
[13]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A Z-Source Inverter (ZSI) based DG system is used. Filters based reference current generation method is employed. Compensate for selective harmonics. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The ZSI involves more passive components. High input ripple and complex control algorithm for ZSI. Use of filters complicates even further the control method. Does not consider symmetrization of unbalanced loads.
[14]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PV system based on voltage control mode is considered. Mitigates for harmonics without a current tracking loop.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Absence of closed control loop on the GSC's line currents. Exposed to over-current conditions may damage the converter. Does not consider symmetrization of unbalanced loads.
[15, 16]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conservative power theory and physical components analysis reference current generation in accordance to prosumers load. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Impose computational problems due to its complexity. Present slow dynamic response.
[Proposed innovative control technique]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A novel OPAHI current controller is employed. Allows on-purpose injection of unbalanced and harmonic currents. Absence of filters and decoupling networks. Computationally less complex among state of the art controllers. Novel <i>PQ</i> controller is used for faster reference current generation based on prosumer load. Reduces power losses, improves grid power quality and reduces the required grid capacity. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Like all the listed controllers, it cannot compensate for DC offset in the grid voltage, which can be compensated by adding a module at $h=0$ in the proposed OPAHI controller. Automatic selection of the most significant harmonics and their possible compensation can be added further.

current controller. The development of the decoupling network based *PQ* controller and the advanced current controller are the main contributions of this paper.

The proposed innovative control technique requires an advanced current controller with improved and faster dynamic response and less oscillations/overshoots at the

for eliminating the undesired $\pm 2\omega$ oscillations. The filters, however, result in slower dynamic response. The problem of slower dynamics is mitigated by an Enhanced Decoupled DSRF (EDDSRF) current controller [20]. The EDDSRF employs a more intelligent and accurate method for the elimination of 2ω oscillations and allows simultaneous injection of both positive and

negative sequence currents. The oscillations that appear on the corresponding positive and negative transformed current vectors are accurately estimated and removed through a cross feedbackdecoupling network. The EDDSRF current controller is however computationally very complex and in addition, the necessary voltage feedforward terms are not used, thereby increasing the control effort of the PI controllers [21].

An equivalent of conventional SRF controller in stationary $\alpha\beta$ frame is proposed in [22] in which, the PI controller is replaced by a Proportional Resonant (PR) controller. The PR controller can compensate for two sequences at a time. However, it has a complicated tuning procedure as it results in higher order transfer function and its operation is jeopardized under off-nominal grid frequencies. In addition, the PR controller does not allow the use of the necessary voltage feedforward terms, imposing in this way an undesired higher control effort on the current controller [23]. Furthermore, considering the complexity of PR and PI controllers, using one PR imposes almost the same complexity as two PI controllers. A combination of Integral (I) and PR controllers are developed in [24-26] for mitigating the effect of unbalanced grid faults and to allow the accurate injection of current. The technique proposed in [27] combines Resonant (R) and PI controllers for the accurate injection of positive sequence current. This controller cannot perform accurately under unbalanced grid conditions and in addition, it is unable to inject the negative sequence current. A current controller mitigating the effect of unbalanced faults is proposed in [28]. It can inject both current sequences separately but not simultaneously. In [29], a combination of PI, R and I controllers is employed to enable the injection of fundamental positive sequence current in the presence of unbalanced faults and harmonics. However, it cannot inject the negative sequence current. All of the current controllers mentioned so far cannot inject both the current sequences simultaneously except the DSRF, the EDDSRF and the controller in [11]. The simultaneous injection in some cases may be required because positive sequence current supports grid in terms of voltage and frequency, whereas the negative sequence current is used to minimize the effect of unbalances caused by grid faults or asymmetric loading conditions. In addition, injecting both positive and negative sequence currents allow the GSC to operate as an active power filter symmetrizing the prosumer's unbalanced loads [1, 8, 11]. The controller in [21] is designed for simultaneous injection of fundamental positive and negative sequence currents with lower complexity but cannot inject harmonics. An

adaptive current controller combining the SRF⁺ and the complex integrals is proposed in [30] for enabling the injection of positive sequence current with unity power factor. This controller does not allow the injection of other current sequences. A filter-based controller enabling the injection of only positive sequence current under grid voltage harmonics is presented in [31]. The injected currents, however, suffer from slow dynamic response due to the presence of filter in the control path [17, 32, 33]. All above mentioned controllers, do not allow the "on-purpose" injection of harmonic currents, necessary for improving the grid power quality by providing non-linear harmonic currents through the GSC of the RES.

The advanced current controller proposed in this work allows the "on-purpose" injection of asymmetric and harmonic currents, thereby removing from the grid the respective asymmetries and harmonics caused by the various non-linear loads and improving the grid power quality. It can also inject the fundamental positive and negative sequences of current, and presents a fast dynamic response with low oscillations and overshoots. All these, are achieved with lower complexity than any of the other methods that appear in the literature. One of the main novel design characteristics of the proposed current controller is the absence of filters in the control path (unlike the DSRF [19] and the EDDSRF [20] controllers) and the avoidance of utilizing decoupling networks (to eliminate oscillations as in the case of the EDDSRF current controller [20]). Thus, the main novelty and contribution of the work is the development of an advanced and less complex current controller for the on-purpose injection of asymmetric and distorted currents and its application towards the multifunctional operation of the GSC of RES using the proposed novel *PQ* controller. The lower complexity ensures the applicability of the method in any commercial inverter, without requiring to employ advanced DSP in order to operate at the given sampling frequency. Furthermore, the proposed method is designed in the *dq* rotating reference frame and it can therefore be applied to any typical RES system as most of such systems are controlled in the *dq*-reference frame. In addition, the designed algorithm is for a typical two-level three-phase converter (and not for a ZSI) which implies that this control method is equally applicable to all the conventional commercial converters. By applying the proposed control method, the benefits for the distribution network observed are the reduction in the power losses, the reduction in distribution network capacity and the improved power quality. Consequently, existing distributed rooftop PV systems can turn into

active grid peripherals providing auxiliary services to the network operators, as will be demonstrated later in this paper.

The proposed current controller for intentionally injecting asymmetric and harmonically distorted currents is presented in Section II.A. Section II.B proposes a novel PQ controller that enables the GSC to act as an active filter for symmetrizing the DN operation and for improving its power quality. The simulation and experimental results validating the performance of the new current controller and of the overall control technique for mitigating the prosumer load asymmetries and harmonics are demonstrated in Section III. The impact to the overall operation of the DN is investigated in Section IV using a realistic distribution grid configuration. The paper concludes in Section V.

II. DESIGN AND ANALYSIS OF THE PROPOSED CONTROL TECHNIQUE

The proposed control technique consists of three parts: the synchronization unit (the DN $\alpha\beta$ PLL [34] is used, because it can work under unbalances and harmonically distorted grid voltages), an advanced current controller (proposed in Section II.A) and a new PQ controller (proposed in Section II.B).

A. Proposed Advanced Current Controller

As mentioned earlier, the EDDSRF is the only current controller that allows the simultaneous injection of positive and negative sequence current. However, the EDDSRF is computationally very complex, does not use the voltage feedforward terms and does not allow the on-purpose injection of harmonic currents. Thus, there is a need to develop an advanced current controller with the ability to inject onpurpose asymmetric and harmonic currents. This paper proposes a new current controller referred to as the OnPurpose Asymmetric and Harmonic Injection (OPAHI) current controller capable of injecting the positive sequence (+), negative sequence (-), and harmonic (h) currents in order to compensate the undesired effects of the grid or the load such as the asymmetric, and the harmonic current components of the prosumer load.

Before the new current controller is proposed and further elaborated, an analysis of grid currents under

abnormal grid/load conditions is provided. The three-phase injected current (\mathbf{i}_{abc}) by a GSC under abnormal grid conditions consists of various current components, that is the positive (\mathbf{i}^{+1}), the negative (\mathbf{i}^{-1}), and the harmonic (\mathbf{i}^h) components of the current:

$$\mathbf{i}_{abc} = \mathbf{i}^{+1} + \mathbf{i}^{-1} + \mathbf{i}^h \tag{1}$$

where, h represents the harmonic order and holds any integer value other than +1 and -1, such as -5, +7, -11... The presence of the extra components such as, -1, and h are due to the abnormal grid voltage conditions or due to the non-linear connected loads. Since the control of the GSC is designed in the *SRF dq*-frame, the behavior of the corresponding currents in the *SRF* domain must be discussed. The three-phase current \mathbf{i}_{abc} is transformed to the corresponding *SRF dq*-frame using (2) and the overall current in the *dq*-frame is given by (3).

$$\mathbf{i}^{n_{dq}} = [T_{dq^n}] ([T_{\alpha\beta}] \mathbf{i}_{abc}) \tag{2}$$

$$\mathbf{i}^{dq} = [T_{\alpha\beta}] = \frac{2}{3} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -\frac{1}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} \\ 0 & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} & -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \end{bmatrix} = T_{dq+1}(\mathbf{i}_{\alpha\beta}) + T_{dq-1}(\mathbf{i}_{\alpha\beta}) + T_{dqh}(\mathbf{i}_{\alpha\beta}) \tag{3}$$

(4)

$$[T_{dq^n}] = [-\text{cossin}((n\theta n\theta)) \text{cossin}((n\theta n\theta))] \tag{5}$$

The transformation angle θ is obtained using a PhaseLocked Loop (PLL). This transformation in (2) with $n=+1$, under normal grid conditions, results in a positive sequence non-oscillating DC term only, \mathbf{i}^{+dq^1} . However, under abnormal grid conditions, the \mathbf{i}^{+dq^1} is accompanied by undesired double, and $(1-h^{th})$ frequency oscillations because of the unbalance sequence ($m=-1$), and harmonic component ($m=h$), respectively, as given by (6). Likewise, if the transformation is carried out with $n=-1$, or h , coupling oscillations are observed

because of the remaining sequences present in the current. The fast and accurate elimination of these oscillations is the key for accurate control in *SRF* using a simple Proportional Integral (PI) controller.

$$\underbrace{I^n \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta_n) \\ \sin(\theta_n) \end{bmatrix}}_{DC \text{ Term}} + \sum \left\{ I^m \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta_m) \\ \sin(\theta_m) \end{bmatrix} \right\}_{Oscillation \text{ Term}}$$

i_{ndq}
 ω
 ω^{\neq}

(6)

All the current controllers addressed in the literature transform the measured currents to dq^{+1} or dq^{-1} or dq^h frames first and then the transformed currents are subsequently subtracted from the reference currents to obtain the error to be provided to the PI controller. This pre-transformation for obtaining the error signal is the main reason why oscillations are observed and decoupling networks are hence needed for their elimination. In contrast, if the error signal is acquired before the frame transformation and the error is subsequently transformed with corresponding speed (+1, -1 or h), no oscillations are observed on the transformed vectors. This novel theoretical idea (feeding the error signals before frame transformation), motivated the development of a new current controller. One of the main design characteristics of the proposed OPAHI current controller is the absence of filters in the control path (unlike the DSRF [19] and the EDDSRF [20] controllers) and the avoidance of utilizing decoupling networks (to eliminate oscillations as in the case of the EDDSRF current controller [20]). Hence, the proposed current controller with advanced operation capabilities presents a faster dynamic response and a lower complexity. The operational capabilities of the new OPAHI current controller allows the PV inverter to act as an active power filter, as will be further on demonstrated in order to enhance the power quality of the DN.

The design details and characteristics of the new OPAHI current controller are:

1. It is designed using multiple SRF frames together with PI controllers; one frame for positive sequence rotating with $+\omega$ speed, one for negative sequence rotating with $-\omega$ speed. Any other frames for

- harmonic current components are rotating with $h\omega$ speeds (where, $h=-5, +7, -11\dots$), as shown in Fig. 1.
2. In each SRF module (positive, negative or harmonic), the reference signals are used as feedforward terms in order to generate the error signals without using the decoupling networks and filters.
3. The only problem in feeding the SRF with the error signal is how to subsequently implement the crosscoupling terms necessary for control implementation, since the cross coupling requires the measured currents and not the error signal. To this end, the measured signals are calculated by a mathematical approach in which the error signal of current is subtracted from the reference current of the corresponding SRF assuming that the controllers in the remaining SRFs achieve a zero error, as shown in Fig. 1.
4. The voltage feedforward terms are used in order to minimize the higher effort imposed on the PI controller. These feedforward terms are obtained from the DN $\alpha\beta$ PLL [34].

The new OPAHI current controller reduces the computational complexity to a significant level due to the complete elimination of decoupling networks, which require large number of Park's transformations and filters as opposed to the ones employed in [19] and [20]. Hence, the proposed

Fig. 1: Proposed OPAHI current controller for on-purpose asymmetric and harmonic current injection.

OPAHI current controller enables the accurate injection of positive sequence, negative sequence and harmonic currents with faster dynamics and less computational resources. It is worth mentioning that the negative and harmonic modules are employed to inject “on-purpose” asymmetric and harmonic currents, allowing the mitigation of asymmetries and harmonics caused by non-linear prosumer loads. The proposed OPAHI current controller is modular and flexible in structure. Thus, in case only positive and negative sequence injection is required, the harmonic module will not be used, and vice versa. The proposed new PQ controller discussed in Section II.B, will determine the amount of asymmetric and harmonic currents required to be injected by the OPAHI current controller for enhancing the power quality.

a. Mathematical Analysis of OPAHI Current Controller

For most of the existing SRF current controllers, the input signal to the PI controller contains undesired oscillations because of the unbalanced and harmonic current components. For such oscillating inputs, the performance of the PI controller is jeopardized as it is designed to track nonoscillating DC references. Decoupling networks and filters are employed to cancel out the double and $(1-h^{th})$ frequency oscillations caused by the negative sequence and harmonic current, and to obtain a non-oscillating current component. However, decoupling networks increase the computational complexity and the use of filters degrade the dynamic response. The OPAHI current controller proposed in this paper does not require additional filters

and decoupling networks. The mathematical analysis in (18) gives the output for the positive module of the OPAHI current controller.

$$\mathbf{v}_{\alpha\beta+1^*} = [T_{d-q1}] ([T_{dq+1}][\Delta\mathbf{i}_{\alpha\beta}][PI]) \quad (7)$$

where, $[T_{dq}^n]$ given in (5) is the transformation matrix used to transform the signals from $\alpha\beta$ to dq frame.

By substituting $\Delta\mathbf{i}_{\alpha\beta} = \mathbf{i}_{\alpha\beta}^{+1^*} + \mathbf{i}_{\alpha\beta}^{-1^*} + \mathbf{i}_{\alpha\beta}^{h^*} - \mathbf{i}_{\alpha\beta}$, (18) can be re-written as:

$${}^{+1^*} \mathbf{v}_{\alpha\beta} = [T_{dq}^{-1}] ([T_{dq}^{+1}] [\mathbf{i}_{\alpha\beta}^{+1^*} + \mathbf{i}_{\alpha\beta}^{-1^*} + \mathbf{i}_{\alpha\beta}^{h^*} - \mathbf{i}_{\alpha\beta}] [PI]) \quad (8)$$

where, $\mathbf{i}_{\alpha\beta+1^*}$, $\mathbf{i}_{\alpha\beta}^{-1^*}$, $\mathbf{i}_{\alpha\beta}$ and $\mathbf{i}_{\alpha\beta}^{h^*}$ are the positive, negative and harmonic reference currents in the stationary reference frame respectively and $\mathbf{i}_{\alpha\beta}$ is the measured current.

Assuming that the accurate (zero error) injection of the negative sequence ($\mathbf{i}_{\alpha\beta}^{-1^*}$) and harmonic ($\mathbf{i}_{\alpha\beta}^{h^*}$) current is ensured through the negative and harmonic modules of the OPAHI controller, (18) can be re-written as (18) by subtracting the measured current ($\mathbf{i}_{\alpha\beta}$) from the sum of negative sequence and harmonic current references.

$${}^{+1^*} \mathbf{v}_{\alpha\beta} = [T_{dq}^{-1}] ([T_{dq}^{+1}] [\mathbf{i}_{\alpha\beta}^{+1^*} - \mathbf{i}_{\alpha\beta}^{+1'}] [PI])$$

(9) where, $\mathbf{i}_{\alpha\beta}^{+1'}$ is the estimated nonoscillating positive sequence current vector in $\alpha\beta$ -frame.

The input to the transformation $[T_{dq}^{+1}]$ in (18) is the error between the reference and the estimated fundamental positive sequence current ($\mathbf{i}_{\alpha\beta}^{+1^*} - \mathbf{i}_{\alpha\beta}^{+1'}$), which is then transformed to $SRF-dq^{+1}$ resulting in an equivalent DC error given in (18), for which, a PI controller provides effective tracking with zero steady state error. The output of the PI controller ($\mathbf{v}_{dq}^{+1^*}$) is transformed back to the stationary $\alpha\beta$ -frame ($\mathbf{v}_{\alpha\beta}^{+1^*}$) and is used for the PWM generation.

$${}^{+1^*} \mathbf{v}_{\alpha\beta} = [T_{dq}^{-1}] \left(\underbrace{[T_{dq}^{+1}] [\mathbf{i}_{\alpha\beta}^{+1^*} - \mathbf{i}_{\alpha\beta}^{+1'}] [PI]}_{\Delta \mathbf{i}_{dq}^{+1}} \right) \quad (10)$$

where, \mathbf{i}_{dq+1^*} is the reference current and $\mathbf{i}^{+dq'}$ corresponds to the amplitude of the estimated non-oscillating positive sequence vector in dq -frame.

Furthermore, it is assumed that the positive and harmonic SRF modules can accurately track their corresponding references \mathbf{i}_{dq+1^*} and $\mathbf{i}_{dq}^{h^*}$ with zero steady state error and thus,

(18) can be used to obtain the output of the negative module of the OPAHI controller.

$${}^{-1^*} \mathbf{v}_{\alpha\beta} = [T_{dq}^{+1}] \left(\underbrace{[\mathbf{i}_{dq}^{-1^*} - \mathbf{i}_{dq}^{-1'}]}_{\Delta \mathbf{i}_{dq}^{-1}} [PI] \right) \quad (11)$$

where, $\mathbf{i}_{dq-1'}$ is the estimated oscillation-free negative sequence current vector in dq -frame.

The input signal $\Delta\mathbf{i}_{dq}^{-1}$ to the PI controller in (18) represents an error between the reference and the estimated negative sequence in dq -frame. The error $\Delta\mathbf{i}_{dq}^{-1}$, however, is a nonoscillating DC vector and therefore, a PI controller can be used to provide fast and accurate tracking.

Similarly, for the harmonic module of the OPAHI controller, the positive and negative $SRFs$ ensure the zero error tracking of their corresponding references and thus, the output of h^{th} harmonic SRF module is given by (18). The PI controller in (18) accurately tracks the provided non-oscillating error $\Delta\mathbf{i}_{dq}^h$ as it is DC in nature.

$$\mathbf{v}_{\alpha\beta}^{h^*} = [T^{-h}] \left(\underbrace{[\mathbf{i}^{h^*} - \mathbf{i}^{h'}] [PI]}_{\Delta \mathbf{i}_{dq}^h} \right) \quad (12)$$

where, $\mathbf{i}^{h'}$ is the estimated oscillation-free h^{th} harmonic current vector.

The overall output of the OPAHI current controller is the sum of each individual module, as given by (18), and is subsequently transferred to the PWM generator.

$$\mathbf{v}_{\alpha\beta}^* = \mathbf{v}_{\alpha\beta}^{+1*} + \mathbf{v}_{\alpha\beta}^{-1*} + \dots + \mathbf{v}_{\alpha\beta}^{h*} \quad (13)$$

By generalizing, the output for n^{th} SRF module of the controller can be expressed by (18).

$$\mathbf{v}_{\alpha\beta}^{n*} = [T_{dq}^{-n}]([T_{dq}^n][\mathbf{i}_{\alpha\beta}^{n*} - \mathbf{i}_{\alpha\beta}^{n'}][PI]) \quad (14)$$

where, $n=+1,-1,+5\dots N$ and $\mathbf{i}_{\alpha\beta}^{n'} = [(\sum_{l \neq n} \mathbf{i}_{\alpha\beta}^{l*}) - \mathbf{i}_{\alpha\beta}]$ is the estimated n^{th} sequence of the injected current.

Equation (14) can be re-written by applying the SRF- dq^n transformation as:

$$\Delta \mathbf{i}_{dq}^{n*} = [T_{dq}^{-n}]^T \left[\mathbf{i}_{dq}^{n*} - \mathbf{i}_{dq}^{n'} \right] [PI] \quad (15)$$

The input signal $\Delta \mathbf{i}_{dq}^{n*}$ of (18) contains non-oscillating terms, and thus, the PI controller can effectively track the corresponding reference currents \mathbf{i}_{dq}^{n*} of the n^{th} sequence. The generalized output for the overall current controller is given in (18), where N shows the total number of modules.

$$\mathbf{v}_{\alpha\beta}^{ref} = [T_{\alpha\beta}]^{-1} \left(\sum_{n=1}^N \mathbf{v}_{\alpha\beta}^{n*} \right) \quad (16)$$

B. Proposed New Advanced PQ Controller (Innovative Control Technique)

The PQ controller generates the reference currents necessary for the extraction of desired real (P) and reactive (Q) powers from the RES and in addition, for the mitigation of asymmetries and harmonic currents (as in the case of the proposed control technique). The proposed PQ controller is divided in two modules, Fig. 2. The first one is the conventional PQ controller responsible for generating the

Fig. 2: An advanced innovative control technique for the GSC of PV systems.

reference currents (\mathbf{i}_{dq}^{+1*}) for the positive module of the current controller in order to ensure that the total generated PV power is delivered to the grid as per the Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) and the Q-profile. The second module is an advanced PQ module, where a decoupling network is used to analyze the prosumer loads and estimates the accurate amount of required negative sequence and/or harmonic currents for their effective compensation. The prosumer load currents are dynamically decoupled into various contained components by the multiple use of (18), for $n=+1,-1,-5,+7\dots$, which is a mathematical realization for the decoupling network.

$$\mathbf{i}_{dq}^{n*} - \mathbf{i}_{dq}^{-L} = [T_{dq}^n] \mathbf{i}_{\alpha\beta}^{n*} \quad (17)$$

The decoupling network therefore accurately estimates the positive sequence (\mathbf{i}_{dq}^{+1-L}), negative sequence (\mathbf{i}_{dq}^{-1-L}) and harmonic (\mathbf{i}_{dq}^{h-L}) components of the load current. From this estimation, the negative and harmonic currents can be directly used as a reference for the current controller of the GSC, that is, $\mathbf{i}_{dq}^{-1*} = \mathbf{i}_{dq}^{-1-L}$ and $\mathbf{i}_{dq}^{h*} = \mathbf{i}_{dq}^{h-L}$. The GSC, thereafter, locally injects the required

amount of asymmetrical -1^* -1^* and h^* harmonically distorted current to the PCC eliminating in this way the undesired effects of harmonics and unbalance on the grid power quality.

For some cases, when the load asymmetries and harmonic distortions are severe and require high current magnitudes, a possibility of violating the GSC's maximum current limit (i_{ml}) can occur. In such cases, the magnitude of the positive sequence current is maintained at its reference value (i_{dq}^{+1*}), whereas the magnitude of the negative sequence and the harmonic current components are reduced to avoid violating the assigned GSC i_{ml} . The maximum value of negative sequence (i_{dq}^{-1*}) and harmonic (i_{dq}^{h*}) currents that can be delivered by the GSC are determined as per (18). Consequently, the magnitude of negative and harmonic currents injected by the GSC must stay below their maximum allowed current limit, i.e. $|i_{dq}| < |i_{dq}|_{max}$ and $|i_{dq}| <$

$|i_{dq}^{h*}|_{max}$. However, in the event that when $|i_{dq}^{-1*}|$ and $|i_{dq}^{h*}|$ exceed the maximum allowed value, the reference currents must be -1^* -1^* reduced h^* h^* to $i_{dq}^{-1*}/|i_{dq}^{-1*}|_{max}$ and $i_{dq}^{h*}/|i_{dq}^{h*}|_{max}$ respectively, in order to ensure the safe and reliable operation of the GSC. In such a case, the GSC still partially compensates for the asymmetries and harmonics but without risking its integrity.

$$|i_{dq}^{-1*}|_{max} = i_{ml} - |i_{dq}^{+1*}| \tag{18}$$

$$|i_{dq}^{h*}|_{max} = i_{ml} - |i_{dq}^{+1*}| - |i_{dq}^{-1*}|$$

An important point to mention is that the work focuses on completely eliminating the grid current unbalance and harmonics and improving the grid power quality to the maximum. If the priority is the compensation of the grid harmonics and asymmetries, this would occur at the expense of the oscillations on the inverter's active/reactive power. However, considering that a certain maximum limit for the inverter power oscillations is desired, the proposed control technique has the ability to limit the amount of compensating currents (asymmetric or harmonic) provided to the load. Thus, the proposed technique can be equally applicable for partially compensating the grid currents while keeping the inverter oscillations within a desired reference level.

In addition, the power oscillations can also be limited when required to operate the inverter under fault ride through conditions. The presence of negative sequence in the grid voltage may either result in the generation of

undesired harmonic currents or cause the inverter's power to oscillate. Various flexible inverter control schemes are presented in [3536] for unbalanced grid voltage faults, where a tradeoff is proposed between the inverter's power oscillations and current harmonics. The authors in [37] propose a control strategy for grid voltage support where it is shown that increasing the amount of asymmetric compensation for the grid voltage recovery increases the inverter's power oscillations and vice versa. In this work however, since we are focusing on the normal operating conditions for the grid voltage (not fault conditions), the voltage asymmetries and harmonics are negligible and as such, inverter power output oscillation reductions are not considered. Consequently, in the proposed case, there would be no oscillations on the inverter power because of the grid voltage. However, on the other hand, for load current unbalance and harmonics, there would always be a tradeoff between the inverter power oscillations and the grid power quality.

III. VALIDATION OF THE PROPOSED CURRENT CONTROLLER

AND OVERALL ADVANCED CONTROL TECHNIQUE

This section validates the performance of the proposed current controller and of the innovative control technique (the new current and the advanced PQ controllers). The simulation and experimental validation is carried out using a sampling rate of 5 kHz on the digitally implemented controller. The maximum order of the harmonic that can be injected by the proposed OPAHI current controller is equal to 1/10 of the sampling rate. Hence, for 5 kHz rate, 9th ($\cong \frac{1}{10} \cdot 5kHz$) harmonic is the maximum order that can be injected. For experimental verifications, the proposed GSC control strategy is implemented in dSPACE DS1104 together with the MATLAB real time interface, a SEMITECH (B6U+E1CIF+B6CI) as the grid tide inverter and an ELEKTRO-AUTOMATIK power supply (EA-PS-9750-20) used as the DC source emulating the generation of PV panels, as shown in Fig. 3.

A. Simulation Results a. Proposed New OPAHI Current Controller

The advanced capability of the proposed current controller for injecting positive sequence, negative sequence and harmonic component is demonstrated in Fig. 4. With zero initial value, the d - and q -axis currents of i_{dq}^{+1} are subjected to a step change of 3 A and 2 A, respectively at 0.4 s. Similarly, the d - and q -axis reference values for i_{dq}^{-1} are changed from zero to 2 A and 1.5 A respectively at 0.5 s. The new OPAHI current control

technique improves the quality of the injected current by improving the controller’s response (reduced oscillations/overshoot and smooth transitions). Following this, +5th and -5th harmonic currents are injected. The magnitudes of i_{dq}^{+5} and i_{dq}^{-5} for both d - and q -axis currents are set to 0.5 A and are respectively injected at 0.6 s and 0.7 s. It is noted that according to Fig. 4, the proposed current controller can inject on-purpose positive sequence, negative sequence and

harmonic distorted currents under any grid condition with faster dynamics and improved performance. It is worth mentioning that the advanced capability of the current controller for injecting positive and negative sequence currents is achieved with lower complexity when compared to other existing methods [20] since the use of decoupling networks and filters is avoided. The computational complexity analysis of the proposed OPAHI current controller and its superiority

(a)

(b)

Fig. 3: Experimental setup employed in the laboratory: (a) a photo (b) a schematic diagram.

to the existing state-of-the-art EDDSRF controller is presented

Fig. 4: Simulation results showing the injection of fundamental positive, negative and harmonic currents using OPAHI current controller.

TABLE II. COMPLEXITY COMPARISON OF CURRENT CONTROLLERS.

Current Controller	Complexity analysis in each control loop					Measured processing time using the TMS320F28335 Microcontroller
	Multisubtractions	PI Controller	$[T_{dq}]$	$[F(s)]$	Total mathematical operations	
EDDSRF ($N=2$) [20]	$(2N-1)$	$2N$	$N+N^2$	N	60 Multiplications 22 Additions 8 Subtractions	$27 \mu s$
Proposed OPAHI ($N=2$)	0	$2N$	$2N$	0	32 Multiplications 12 Additions 4 Subtractions	$14.4 \mu s$
Extended EDDSRF* ($N=9$)	$(2N-1)$	$2N$	$N+N_2$	N	642 Multiplications 149 Additions 107 Subtractions	$282.4 \mu s$
Proposed OPAHI ($N=9$)	0	$2N$	$2N$	0	144 Multiplications 54 Additions 18 Subtractions	$64.8 \mu s$

N = number of sequences a controller can inject. *In literature EDDSRF exists for $N=2$ only, but if in case it is extended for harmonic injection.

in Table II. The computational analysis is carried out in two ways. Firstly, by considering the number of algebraic manipulations (additions, subtractions and multiplications for each current controller) required in each control loop as listed in Table II. Secondly, by measuring the processing time taken by each current controller when employed in the Texas Instrument TMS320F28335, a widely used microcontroller for such power electronic applications. According to the analysis, the proposed OPAHI current controller (for $N=2$) is 46.66 % less complex when compared to [20]. For harmonic injection ($N>2$), a comparison of the proposed OPAHI current controller is made with the possible extension of the existing state-of-the-art EDDSRF current controller, which originally exists only for the injection of positive and negative sequence currents. If the EDDSRF is extended for harmonic injection, the computational complexity of the proposed OPAHI current controller is 77 % less compared to the extended EDDSRF current controller, as analyzed in Table II.

b. Operation of the GSC under the Innovative Control Technique (Advanced PQ and Current Controller)

The operation of the GSC under the proposed advanced control technique is demonstrated in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6. In Fig. 5, all the three phases of the load current are symmetrical until $t=0.4$ s, hence the three-phase current drawn from the grid is also symmetrical. However, at $t=0.4$ s a step change of 1 kW is applied to phase b and c, causing asymmetry. Consequently, the three-phase current demanded by load becomes asymmetric, requiring negative sequence of current. Until 0.5 s, the advanced control technique is not activated, hence the negative sequence component of current is drawn from the grid, Fig. 5. However, at $t=0.5$ s, the proposed control technique is activated and the negative sequence current is locally generated by the GSC of the PV system, making the grid current symmetrical by delivering the required amount of the negative current.

Furthermore, a step change of 0.9 kW is again applied to phase b and c at 0.6 s. In this case, a small amount of asymmetric current is drawn from the grid because the GSC's maximum current limits are reached (severe asymmetry) and the injection of the negative sequence current is limited for the safe operation of GSC switches. After 0.7 s, the control technique is again deactivated and all the asymmetric current is drawn from the grid.

The result in Fig. 5 verifies the effectiveness of proposed control scheme for mitigating the undesired asymmetric effects of prosumer load.

Fig. 5: Mitigation of prosumer's asymmetries using proposed control scheme.

Fig. 6: Mitigation of prosumer's harmonics using proposed control technique.

Likewise, the proposed technique is also effective for the mitigation of harmonics generated by the prosumer's nonlinear load (as shown in Fig. 6). The connected load

in this case requires a positive sequence current of 11.6 A per each phase and a 5th harmonic component with a magnitude of 0.5 A. Until 0.4 s, the proposed innovative control technique for the harmonic mitigation is deactivated, so the harmonic current is drawn from the grid. However, after 0.4 s when the proposed control technique is activated, the harmonic current is injected locally via the GSC and the grid current becomes free of harmonic distortions. Furthermore, at $t=0.5$ s a step change of 0.5 kW is applied to phases b and c of the connected load, resulting in the asymmetric harmonic current required by the load. As the proposed control technique is activated, the asymmetric and harmonic current is delivered by the GSC of the PV system and thus, the flow of current from the grid remains harmonic free and symmetrical. This verifies the new functional mode of GSC for enhancing the power quality between the grid and the prosumer.

B. Experimental Results a. Proposed New OPAHI Current Controller

The new OPAHI current controller is investigated for three case studies. For all three cases, the injected d and q axis positive sequence currents are for 1200 W active and 0 VAR reactive power, respectively. The first case validates the injection of negative sequence current together with the positive sequence, as shown in Fig. 7, along with a comparison with the simulation results. With zero initial value, i_{d^-1ref} is subjected to a step change of 1 A at 158.34 s. Consequently, the current controller continues to inject balanced sinusoidal currents until 158.34 s, and thereafter the injected current becomes “on-purpose” asymmetrical. This validates the asymmetric current injection capability of the proposed OPAHI current controller. In addition to the experiments, simulation results are also added in the same figure in order to clearly show the agreement

between the two. The experimental d - and q -axis currents are shown in purple and green color, respectively. On the other hand, the simulated d - and q -axis currents are displayed in blue and pink color, respectively. The proposed OPAHI controller enables fast and accurate injection of the positive and negative sequence currents with rise and settling time of less than 0.1 ms. The experimental results in Fig. 7 are measurements obtained from the dSPACE control desk and reproduced in MATLAB because the number of the oscilloscope channels was limited to four. Thus, in this paper, for demonstrating more than four experimental signals, the dSPACE is used to obtain the measurements, which are reproduced in MATLAB.

The performance of the OPAHI controller is further validated through the injection of harmonic current component, as shown in Fig. 8 (a). The positive sequence injection corresponds 1200 W active and 0 VAR reactive powers. The initial value of i_{q^-5ref} is set to zero and later on it is subjected to a step change of 1 A at the point marked with the red arrow. At this instant, the OPAHI controller enables fast and accurate injection of the harmonic current with almost zero oscillations and no overshoot, and within a response time of less than 0.1 ms.

The third case study analyzes the performance of OPAHI when all the three components, that is, fundamental positive sequence, negative sequence and -5th harmonic are injected simultaneously, Fig. 8 (b). The OPAHI controller continues to inject positive sequence (4 A), negative sequence (1 A) and at the point marked with red arrow the q -component of -5th harmonic is injected with a magnitude of 0.5 A. The grid current is asymmetric from the start and later on it becomes

Fig. 7: Experimental results validating the simultaneous injection of fundamental positive and negative current sequences along with a comparison with the simulation results.

“on-purpose” harmonically distorted. The response time of the OPAHI controller is very fast, as can be seen that, it takes almost 0.1 ms to reach and settle at the reference value. The fast and accurate performance of OPAHI is verified for all the three case studies presented. It is worth mentioning that the proposed OPAHI is the most flexible controller compared to the other ones discussed because in addition to unbalance currents, it allows the on-purpose injection of harmonic currents as well.

Fig. 8: Experimental results validating the simultaneous injection of fundamental positive, negative and harmonic current sequences.

b. Operation of the GSC under the Innovative Control Technique (Advanced PQ and Current Controller)

The significance of the proposed control scheme is experimentally demonstrated by an interaction between the prosumer’s three-phase load current I_{Load} , the PV injected current I_{PV} and the current exchanged between

the prosumer and the grid I_G . In the first case study, the proposed innovative control scheme is always activated and the prosumer load changes at $t = 0.185$ s. In particular, the RMS load currents of the prosumer (absorbed by the load bank of the experimental setup) are set to $[i_{a-rms} \ i_{b-rms} \ i_{c-rms}] = [0.66 \text{ A} \ 2.05 \text{ A} \ 2.05 \text{ A}]$ for $t < 0.185$ s, and at 0.185 s they are modified to $[i_{a-rms} \ i_{b-rms} \ i_{c-rms}] = [0.66 \text{ A} \ 0.95 \text{ A} \ 0.66 \text{ A}]$ including an absorption of 1% 5th harmonic, as shown in Fig. 9. The innovative control scheme can instantly sense the prosumer’s load change and react accordingly in order to regulate the current injection by the PV to compensate the asymmetries imposed by the new load within 39 ms. Therefore, the current exchanged between the prosumer and the grid, I_G , becomes symmetrical and the power quality of the distribution grid is ensured.

In the second case, the ICT is activated and deactivated between certain time periods to demonstrate the clear impact of the proposed control technique on the current exchanged between the prosumer and the grid I_G , as shown in Fig. 10. For $t < 0.18$ s, the flexible control scheme is deactivated. During this time, the PV is injecting symmetrical current and the unbalanced prosumer loads are directly affecting the grid current, making it highly asymmetrical. In the same case study, when the proposed ICT is activated at $t > 0.18$ s, PV injects all the asymmetric currents locally by the GSC and the exchange of current between the grid and the prosumer become symmetrical, improving therefore the power quality of the distribution grid. The proposed control scheme allows a faster compensation of asymmetric load currents with a response time of approximately 37 ms. The time response of 37 ms is required for compensating 90% of asymmetries. However, for compensating 99% of asymmetries, the control algorithm requires 200 ms in total (which corresponds to the steady state for the overall controller). As can be seen in Fig 10 (b), from 0.38 s to 0.54 s, under steady state the grid currents are completely symmetrical. It is important to mention that PQ and current controllers are the hierarchical controllers. Thus, the inner loop (current controller) present very fast dynamics (less than 0.1ms response time) while the outer loop (PQ controller)

Asymmetric current required by load

Fig. 10: Experimental results validating the significance of proposed innovative control scheme for the effective mitigation of prosumers abnormalities (a) mitigation of 90 % asymmetries (response time 37 ms), (b) steady state operation (complete elimination of asymmetries).

need to be slower for stability reason and that is why it presents slower dynamics.

IV. IMPACT OF ADVANCED GSC CONTROL TECHNIQUE ON A REALISTIC DISTRIBUTION NETWORK

The mitigation of asymmetries and elimination of harmonics can significantly reduce the power losses, improve the usage of grid capacity and improve the power quality of distribution network (DN). The significance of the proposed advanced control technique for PVs is further investigated by applying this method on several residential PVs installed on a realistic small-scale low-voltage DN model. The parameters of the distribution grid are according to the Electricity Authority of Cyprus (EAC) grid. For the purpose of this investigation, the DN consists of 6 buses

Fig. 9: Experimental results validating the significance of proposed innovative control scheme for effective mitigation of prosumers abnormalities.

in total, with some buses consisting of normal consumer loads and others representing prosumers, as shown in Fig. 11. Single and three-phase consumer loads are connected on buses 1 and 4, whereas for enabling the existence of prosumers in the DN, buses 2, 3, 5 and 6 consist of three-phase rooftop PV systems along with the consumer loads. Bus number 6 consists of a 5th-order harmonic absorption load, added intentionally to justify the compensation of harmonics and to demonstrate the impact of proposed technique to the power quality. To examine and demonstrate the impact to the DN, the control systems are equipped with the proposed OPAHI current controller and the advanced PQ control scheme. The OPAHI current controller is used at all times, whereas the advanced innovative control technique will be activated and deactivated to justify its significance and impact.

The impact of the proposed Innovative Control Technique (referred to as ICT) on the distribution network is investigated under different operating conditions. The operating conditions include, (i), The PV rooftops injecting symmetrical currents (with ICT deactivated), (ii), PV injection enabled using proposed ICT and (iii), operation of DN when PV rooftops are completely disconnected. The performance enhancement resulting by employing the proposed innovative control technique is analyzed by observing the three-phase current (I_{abc}), the active (P) and reactive (Q) powers drawn from the Low Voltage (LV) side of the distribution grid MV/LV transformer, as shown in Fig. 12. Furthermore, measured quantities on bus no. 6 (end of the feeder), presented in Fig. 13, are used to analyze and reflect on the clear improvement in

Fig. 11: One-line diagram for realistic distribution grid of Cyprus.
MV: Medium Voltage and LV: Low Voltage

Fig. 12: Impact of proposed innovative control scheme on the power drawn from distribution grid.

the quality of power drawn from the grid using the proposed ICT.

Examining the results in Fig. 12, when all the PV rooftop systems are injecting symmetrical currents between 0.25 s to 0.35 s, the current drawn from the grid is harmonically distorted and highly asymmetrical due to the presence of unbalanced and non-linear loads. The proposed ICT is not activated during this time span. Considering the second operating condition between 0.35 s to 0.45 s, the proposed ICT is activated and corresponding improvement in the grid currents are clearly seen. The current drawn from the grid is harmonic-free and almost symmetrical. The small asymmetry observed in the current is because the proposed ICT cannot be used on buses 1 and 4 due to the absence of PVs. The corresponding active and reactive power oscillations which occurred as a result of the negative sequence and harmonic current initially drawn from the grid are now reduced due to ICT activation (since these non-linear load currents of prosumers at buses 2, 3, 5 and 6 are now locally generated by the PV systems). Furthermore, when the PVs are disconnected (between 0.45 s and 0.55 s), the grid currents become again asymmetrical and distorted. In addition, the amount of active power drawn, and the oscillations in active and reactive power are also observed to increase.

Similar conclusions are obtained from Fig. 13 showing the results for the bus no. 6 of the DN. When operated without the ICT activated, the current drawn

by bus no. 6 from the grid is asymmetrical and harmonically distorted. However, at 0.35 s when ICT is activated the grid currents become harmonic free and symmetrical. The corresponding active and reactive power oscillations are completely eliminated. During 0.35 to 0.45, all the distorted and asymmetric currents required by the loads are provided by the PV system, as can be seen from Fig. 13.

Fig. 13: Impact of proposed innovative control technique on DN (specifically for bus 6, containing both asymmetric and harmonic loads). GB6: grid current at bus 6, LB6: load current at bus 6, PVB6: PV current delivered to bus 6.

TABLE III. POWER QUALITY ANALYSIS OF THE DISTRIBUTION GRID

Operating Conditions	DN power losses (W)	Required DN capacity (A)	Power quality at MV/LV transformer	
			$(v^- + v^h)/ v^+ $	$(i^- + i^h)/ i^+ $
(i) PV injecting symmetrical currents	452	89.1	0.64	10.59
(ii) PV operating as per proposed ICT	427	74.5	0.077	1.50
(iii) PV disconnected	635	104.2	0.55	8.83

A detailed analysis of the proposed ICT on the overall operation of the distribution network is presented in Table III. The analysis presents the power losses, the required DN capacity for satisfying the loads and the power quality at the LV side of the MV/LV transformer for all the three operating conditions. The power quality is assessed by calculating the ratio between the negative sequence and harmonic component magnitude to the magnitude of positive sequence, that is, for current the

ratios is $(|i^-|+|i^h|)/|i^+|$ and for voltage it is $(|v^-|+|v^h|)/|v^+|$. These indices determine the level of asymmetries and harmonics present in the grid voltage and current. For cases (i) and (iii), the performance indices have the highest values, representing the lower power quality of the DN. The highest values observed in case (i) are because the PV is injecting some part of the symmetric current (i^+), whereas the asymmetric (i^-) and harmonic (i^h) currents are completely drawn from the grid MV/LV transformer. However, examining case (ii), both of these indices result in very low values, indicating the significant improvement in the power quality of the DN. The majority of asymmetric and harmonic distorted currents are delivered locally through the GSC of the PV in case (ii), and this is the reason for the improved power quality.

The DN power losses are obtained by calculating the difference between the total generated power (the power from grid and the PV) and the power consumed by the load. The DN power losses are highest when the PVs are not connected and are significantly reduced under the case scenario (i), when PVs are integrated (since the required power for serving the loads is generated in a distributed way), resulting in 28.8% less power losses. These losses are further decreased by 5.5%, when the PVs are operated with the proposed ICT. The further reduction of losses is achieved since the operation of the LV DN is symmetrized and the currents are fairly allocated between the three phases. The calculation of losses considers only the LV network. The impact of the proposed method will become more significant if the power losses caused by the asymmetric and non-linear loading of the Medium Voltage (MV) are also considered. The effect on the capacity of DN transformers and lines is also presented in Table III. The DN capacity is calculated by measuring the magnitude of the current at the LV side of MV/LV transformer. It can be seen that the presence of distributed PVs reduce the required grid capacity by 14.51% compared to when there are no PVs due to the distributed generation. The DN capacity is further reduced by 16.38% when the PV injection is enabled with the proposed innovative control technique due to fair allocation of the load currents among the three-phases. The reduced power losses, the improved power quality and the effective utilization of the distribution capacity demonstrate the substantial impact of the proposed innovative control scheme to the overall operation of the DN.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper proposes a new current controller for the fast and accurate injection of on-purpose asymmetric and harmonic distorted currents using the GSC of RES. The proposed innovative control scheme allows the development of a flexible and diversified functional mode for PV inverters that can mitigate the asymmetries and harmonics caused by the non-linear prosumer loads. The impact of the proposed control technique is demonstrated on a realistic low-voltage distribution network. The experimental and simulation results demonstrate significant improvement to the grid power quality, lower power losses and reduced distribution network capacity and verify the substantial impact of the work.

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